

Figure 5. Eligibility Criteria.		
Inclusion Description	Exclusion Description	Exclusion Reason and Description
<p>ToxRTool applied to assess reliability (of studies)</p> <p>ToxRTool modified to assess reliability without any specific application</p> <p>ToxRTool modified to assess reliability and applied to assess reliability (of studies)</p> <p>ToxRTool applied to assess risk of bias (RoB)</p> <p>ToxRTool or ToxRTool modification is applied to assess other study aspects that are not reliability or RoB</p> <p>Other (for unspecified category)</p>	<p>Only cited (no discussion, details, or description)</p> <p>No discussion of how or why ToxRTool was selected and/or applied</p> <p>Review</p>	<p><i>Low quality English translation: After translating the non-English article using one or all three translation applications, the results are suspect and low quality to provide accurate information for data extraction.</i></p> <p><i>Only cited in references section: Authors did not discuss ToxRTool anywhere in the article and only cited it in their references.</i></p> <p><i>Review, secondary discussion of ToxRTool: Describes the type of article that is not a primary source (may be paired with the tag “secondary discussion of ToxRTool.”</i></p> <p><i>No discussion, no application: Authors describe and discuss how ToxRTool can be used, but there is no clear application of ToxRTool for the project presented in the article.</i></p> <p><i>No mention of ToxRTool: The article has no listing or mention of ToxRTool anywhere in the document.</i></p>
<p>Figure 5. Eligibility Criteria. This table describes what conditions would include or exclude a publication. Exclusion reasons and descriptions are also includes as this is an option in Covidence.</p>		